

Visceral Hedonic Rhetoric: Emerging Research in Design and Emotion

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Abstract

This paper aims to identify areas for future investigation so that products may be designed to harness the full potential of users' visceral responses. It lays the foundation for this work by discussing the scope, significance and limitations of currently available research in the areas of Visceral Design, Consumer Hedonics and Product Rhetoric. Concerned as it is with instinctual, emotional responses, visceral hedonics is of vital importance to the design discipline. A better understanding of this area will enable designers to instantly create powerful emotional connections between consumers and products. This understanding can be furthered by investigating consumers' visceral hedonic responses to a variety of products and the product attributes that elicit these responses, and suggests directions for emerging research.

Conference theme: design and emotion theoretical issues

Keywords: visceral design, hedonics, product rhetoric

Introduction

All products elicit some kind of emotional response from the consumer, be it good, bad, intentional or non-intentional (Gomez, Popovic and Bucolo, 2005). An emotional attachment between product and user is paramount to the success or failure of a product (Overbeeke and Hekkert, 1999). Emotional responses can incite consumers to select a particular product from a row of similar products and will, therefore, have a considerable influence on purchase decisions. As a consequence, more and more products are challenging designers to consider the emotional impact of their work and to design for emotional experiences. As fledgling as this field is, a lack of conceptual clarity exists in the area of emotional design (Norman, 2004; Desmet, 2002; Forlizzi, Disalvo and Hanington, 2000).

According to Norman (2004), emotional design encompasses multifarious behaviours, including a visceral level of unconscious cognition and emotional processing through which the user reacts to the visual and other sensory aspects of a product (Meikle, 2005). The visceral involves an automatic evaluation of perceived properties of product rhetoric and has the power to make consumers feel good about the product they are about to purchase. It is this instantaneous, hedonic response induced by a product that needs to be more systematically addressed by designers. However, there is a lack of current research on specific causes of visceral reactions (Norman, 2004).

Even though there is a general consensus about the nature of visceral design (Houghton, Calvert, Jackson, Cooper and Whorwell, 2002), little information exists on how an individual's emotional, hedonic responses relate to visceral product properties (Loewenstein, 1996). Product rhetoric — which encompasses the persuasive features of the designed product that induce a hedonic response through the visceral level of emotional cognition — is clearly implicated in this relationship. Thus, this paper isolates and explores available research in the three areas of (i) visceral design, (ii) consumer hedonics and (iii) product rhetoric (Figure 1) in order to provide a platform to identify future research needs in the area of emotional design. While each of these categories has been the subject of (limited) individual study, they have not been collectively studied, and not in relation to product design. In the following sections, each of these terms will be explained and its relevance to the study highlighted. Finally, the paper introduces an emerging research area — visceral hedonic rhetoric — a conglomerate approach which will address the gaps identified in the current literature in these three specific areas.

Figure 1: Research areas

Visceral Design

Norman (2004) argues that the three levels of cognition and emotional processing — which consist of *visceral*, *behavioural* and *reflective* — should be addressed in that order by product designers. The behavioral level of cognition occurs after the visceral, and defines product behaviors that complement a user’s own actions, implicit assumptions, and instinctive usability and interaction. Of the three levels, Norman (2004) contemplates that behavioral design is the most familiar to designers and an area of much established research. Reflective design is the least immediate component of mental processing, and involves conscious consideration and reflection on past experiences. Reflective processing can enhance or inhibit behavioral processing, but has no direct access to visceral reactions. This level of cognitive processing is accessible only via memory, not through direct interaction or perception. An articulated structure of all three levels is provided by Norman (2004) and helps in the design of products to elicit specific user responses, and in validating assumptions that were long held by designers.

Visceral design is the cognitive processing of immediate responses by which the user reacts to visual and other sensory aspects of a product before significant interaction occurs (Norman, 2004). Visceral design involves recognition of the initial impact that a product makes on a

consumer, occurs instantaneously, and allows consumers to make rapid decisions about what is good, bad, safe or dangerous. Many authorities have tried to define the visceral as it is used in many different contexts and across a broad scale (Norman, 2004; Loewenstein, 1996; Langerderfer, Shimp, 2001; Givochi, Velazquez, 2001). An experience that consumers are unable to control as they fall victim to the visceral factors of a product are not only imperative to a successful design, but are embedded in the unconscious psyche (Stead, Goulev, Evans, and Mamdani, 2004).

An individual's senses are directly affected by visceral design, and designing for what the senses initially perceive, is classified as designing for the visceral level (Norman, 2004). Instinctual reactions of survival (which are regulated by the brain) are the most basic levels of cognition, and property aspects such as colour, texture, shape and sound are sensory aspects of appearance that create instinctual reactions which, in turn, provoke positive or negative product responses in consumers (Meikle, 2005). It is the nature of these responses that are unexplored and unrecorded in visceral hedonic design research. Most of the information on this topic is very broad and no actual case studies focus directly on visceral hedonics. Add to this the evident lack of research linking visceral hedonic responses to products and their corresponding design properties, and the lack of understanding in this field becomes quite significant.

Consumer Hedonics

The branch of psychology that studies the mind's pleasant and unpleasant sensations is classified as hedonics. Hedonics is identified as anything relating to the pursuit of pleasure (Porter, Chibber and Porter, 2001; Hirshman and Holbrook, 1982) and can also be described as the emotional state of pleasure or displeasure that an individual feels (Barrett, Mesquita, Ochsner, and Gross, 2007).

Hedonics is also convincingly significant to consumers, and the study of hedonics in design aims to examine how an individual actively pursues pleasure by selecting certain products above others. A consumer's hedonic choices are the decisions made by the consumer to purchase a product for its enjoyment, pleasure and excitement. While consumers have often reported wanting functional or tangible attributes when purchasing products, there is also a demand for a hedonic or satisfying emotional response and experience when using a product (McDonald, 1998). In brief, hedonic consumption relates to facets of a consumer's behaviour that relate to aspects of the product purchase and handling experience, and to the multi sensory, fantasy and emotive aspects of product usage (Hirschman and Holbrok, 1982).

Needless to say, hedonics is important to a product's success and is considered in the design industry in the pursuit of pleasurable design (Porter, Chibber, and Porter, 2001). Limited information exists regarding consumers' subjective perceptions and preferences which concern a product's hedonic value. Crusen and Snelders (2002) hold that consumers derive aesthetic pleasure from the appearance of a product by the way in which they are attracted to, and evaluate it through, its presentation and shape, while Jordan (2000) believes that a consumer's pleasure is maximized when a product is designed especially to suit their needs and desires. Jordan (2000) states that the links between pleasure and product properties are assumptions and speculation only, and the next stage is to link the desire for pleasure to particular characteristics of product design. The way in which consumers initially react to a product demonstrates how intense a hedonic product experience actually is (Campbell, 1987). Products that consumers choose were validated and measured by a large qualitative study where an answering machine was used to analyze consumer responses to product properties (Crusen and Snelders, 2002). However, whether the responses were hedonic responses or other sensory responses (such as visceral, emotional or aesthetic) is unknown. The need to separate and compare responses and to determine their triggers still presents a significant gap in the literature. It is an issue that must be thoroughly addressed if any significant contribution to design is to be made (Jordan, 2000).

Above all, consumer hedonics is important to this study due to its close relation to visceral design through the immediacy of consumer of consumer response and reaction.

Product Rhetoric

Throughout history rhetoric has been defined as the art of speaking well or the art of persuasive verbal communication. Over the years it has developed interdisciplinary associations with the common goal of strategically effective communication (Erlhoff and Marshall, 2007).

According to Erlhoff and Marshall (2007) the application of rhetoric to the design field takes place on two levels. The first level involves offering practical information; for example: on presenting knowledge and ideas, structuring and shaping communication and on the art of memorizing. The second level involves the possibility of deriving higher order models. These models describe the relationship between theory and practice, between production and analysis, as well as the process of rhetorical communications (Erlhoff and Marshall, 2007). Rhetoric can inevitably vary in substance but not necessarily by form: "it is even probable that there exists a single rhetorical form" (Barthes, 1977: 49). This means that the rhetoric of an artifact is specific

to the extent to which it is subject to the physical constraints of vision (Barthes, 1977). Buchanan (2001) believes that rhetoric in products plays an imperative role for two reasons. Firstly, technology exerts a strong and growing influence on product design in the 21st century. Secondly, there is an increasing distance between the two professions of technology and design. He also suggests a suitable theory of rhetoric in design would be one in which technology is viewed fundamentally as a rhetorical problem, to be integrated within the field of design and not the other way around (Buchanan, 1995). He even goes on to suggest that the “designer, instead of simply making an object is actually creating a persuasive argument that comes to life whenever a user considers or uses that product as a means to some form of end” (Buchanan, 1985: 8).

In the wider field of design, however, there is currently no unifying theme of rhetoric and a unifying theory of rhetoric remains unexplored. This is surprisingly incongruous when latent issues of communication and rhetoric in design exert a strong influence on the understanding of all objects made for human use and where communication is a significant part of the design process (Barthes, 1977). But rhetoric is undergoing a new era of research and development, with designers helping to shape it to meet modern contemporary demands (Kaufer and Butler, 1996). If designers can benefit from rhetorical insights, then design can continue to influence and form society through its persuasive assertions. Uncovering what designers need to discover is an entirely new aspect of demonstrative rhetoric which will significantly affect the understanding of product influence in the future.

The category of product rhetoric is not new; nor is it a widely explored area of research. However, reconciling product rhetoric with the visceral hedonic responses, positions rhetoric in an entirely new area of research. Product rhetoric describes the research in terms of persuasive product design properties and focuses on the features that enable products to communicate convincingly. In relation to visceral hedonics, it grounds the study in the field of product design.

Visceral Hedonic Rhetoric

It is the proposition of this study that a combination of the visceral design, consumer hedonics, and product rhetoric categories, can assist in identifying the visceral hedonic rhetoric in product design. The aim is to address the current research in each area and to then determine the necessary directions for future research.

From a broader perspective, there is a copious amount of research on purchaser behavior from a psychological and business perspective (Loewenstein, 1996). No research, however, considers it from a design perspective. While purchasing decisions are analysed according to brand, reputation and impulse purchasing (Givechi and Velazquez, 2001), there is no information available to explain why consumers respond to visceral hedonic features and whether, and to what degree, those features influence their purchasing behaviour. This information would greatly assist understanding in emotional design. Furthermore, the visceral emotional response that may influence consumers' decisions might be the key to understanding product rhetoric.

Over the last ten years, emotional design has become a popular area of research (Westwood, 2005). Emotional responses have been studied in relation to individual products (Desmet, 2002). However, the current research does not address how an individual's emotional responses occur in relation to visceral product properties and how that relates to consumer hedonics. This is the main research gap that needs to be addressed. Table 1 summarises the relevant research and demonstrates significant research gaps. Again, it shows that knowledge of this topic is very general and no actual and specific case studies have been undertaken. Two major gaps identified from the literature review demonstrate that:

- 1 there are no specific studies of visceral hedonics and its relationship to product design;
- 2 there is no available information linking the study of visceral hedonic behaviour to product use, consumption, physical design features or purchase decisions.

Author	Year	Summary
Buchanan	2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rhetoric in design plays a vital role • suggestions of designers producing an object that comes pre-programmed with a persuasive agenda • comments that products are vehicles for argument and persuasion about the desirable qualities of life
Crusen and Snelders	2002	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pleasure is derived aesthetically from products • appearance and shape influence consumer choices • large qualitative study (of consumer response to answering machines) which tried to establish the importance of the categories within the product's appearance that were appealing to consumers
Desmet	2002	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establishment of emotions and their role in designed products • emergence of interest in emotionally designed products • clarification of the relationship between product appearance and the emotional response elicited by a consumer
Forlizzi, Disalvo and	2000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • philosophical and cognitive science understanding of emotion and experience

Hanington		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attempt to produce a generative framework to aid designers in harnessing emotional experiences • transfer of theories of emotion and experience into frameworks that transcend into methodologies for design practice
Jordan	2000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identification of pleasure based approaches to human factors in product design • design of pleasurable products in relation to the hedonic factors in product designs • linking of product benefits to product properties
Loewenstein	1996	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description of the ‘visceral’ as a sensation of being out of control • discussion of visceral factors such as hunger, thirst, sexual desire, emotion and pain • admission that visceral factors have a direct hedonic impact on people’s actions • establishment of link between hedonic and visceral reactions
Norman	2004	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establishment of three levels of emotional cognition in unconscious processing: visceral, behavioural and reflective • allowing products to produce controlled user responses

Table 1: Literature review summary

This summary demonstrates that there needs to be a stronger research emphasis on the interrelationship of visceral design, consumer hedonics and product rhetoric properties and responses and establishes the foundation for this emerging research.

Emerging Research

This paper has introduced an emerging study that will explore the visceral hedonic rhetoric design elements of a product and will employ an empirical approach to understand how consumers respond viscerally to hedonic rhetoric. It aims to holistically address the limitations evidenced by the literature review in all focus areas of visceral design, hedonic responses and product rhetoric. The current research also suggests that, in order to identify what exactly causes a visceral hedonic response, participant interaction with specific products and everyday objects must be examined.

From this platform, the research proposition and research questions have been derived:

Research Proposition:

To explore the visceral hedonic rhetoric evident in the design of interactive products.

Research Questions:

How does different visceral rhetoric in products affect hedonic responses?

How do visceral hedonic responses differ between novice and expert users of products?

The experiment has the following objectives:

- To identify visceral product properties evident in interactive products
- To explore the hedonic responses to product rhetoric

Everyday, popular and ‘trendy’ consumer products — such as digital cameras, laptops, GPS and mobile telephones — will be targeted for the study due to their broad range of usage. Participants who are expected to be involved with the study will represent a wide demographic of age and product experience. An initial interview will be conducted to gather personal information about the participants’ demographics and background, as well as to help determine how familiar they are with the product. It will also act as a screening process to select the most suitable participants.

Objective A will be explored in Experiment 1 (Table 2). Its purpose is to extract data pertaining to the participants’ visceral responses. From an analysis of this data, categories of visceral responses will emerge. They will become the foundations for Experiment 2 that will respond to *Objective B* (Table 3).

	Experiment 1
Setting	HCRU laboratory, D Block, Queensland University of Technology, Gardens Point Campus.
Time	20 minutes
Methods	Observation
Data collection	Using the digital video cameras and recorders in the research laboratory
Experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • six interactive products will be placed in front of individual participants • each participant will be asked a series of questions • each participant is asked to respond very quickly • the participants’ responses are recorded
Data analysis tools	Atlas.ti will be used to analyse the text data and Noldus Observer will be used to analyse the observational data
Participants	10 participants aged between 18 and 24
Materials	6 interactive products

Table 2: Experiment 1 summary - Objective A

Objective B will be investigated using Experiment 2 (Table 3). Findings of Experiment 1 (*Objective A*, Table 1) will specifically determine how the interactive products are presented

to the participants. The aim is to individually isolate and analyse their visceral responses. This experiment will need to be repeated with different probes in order to mask and highlight various visceral attributes.

	Experiment 2
Setting	HCRU laboratory located in D Block, Queensland University of Technology, Gardens Point campus.
Time	15 minutes
Method	Observation and questionnaire
Data collection	Using the digital video cameras and recorders in the research laboratory
Experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • six interactive products will be simultaneously exposed to the participant • interaction time will be controlled • researcher will instruct the participant to rank the products in order of preference • the final choice will be recorded
Data analysis tool	Atlas.ti will be used to analyse the text data and Noldus Observer will be used to analyse the observational data
Participants	30 (screened) participants with a targeted demographic and representing the spectrum of novice to expert users
Materials	6 interactive products

Table 3: Experiment 2 summary – Objective B

Conclusion

In this paper, a literature review has demonstrated that each category of visceral design, consumer hedonics and product rhetoric has been separately investigated. It then highlights the limitations of this research and the need to explore these three areas in the conglomerate, emerging research area of visceral hedonic rhetoric pertinent to consumer response to and, therefore, to the design of, interactive products.

The subsequently proposed study is designed to serve three significant purposes. Firstly, it will identify the visceral hedonic rhetoric involved in participants' pursuit of products. Secondly it will provide information that will help identify and understand consumer behaviour and purchase decisions. Thirdly, it will assist designers in designing and developing new products by harnessing the full potential of visceral hedonic rhetoric. Furthermore, this research in the emerging field of visceral hedonic rhetoric will inform the area of emotional design, other design domains, and other disciplines relating to consumer behaviour.

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